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An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Hcg26.

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We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of histocompatibility gene product Hcg26 as a candidate gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.